

PHYSICOCHEMICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON PARTICLES IN BLOOD

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ABSTRACT

Our ecosystem is contaminated with pollutants. Aerial, aquatic and soil, all are loaded with pollutants either intentionally or by natural calamities. But anthropogenic pollutants qualitatively and quantitatively are more problematic and derogative structurally and functionally. Pollutants are dominated with carbon particles and other particulate matter which are released in ecosystem randomly and in unplanned manner. The carbon particles are the product of incomplete combustion while particulate matter is the result of unorganized anthropogenic activities over the globe. Rich countries and industrial set-ups discard such wastes either pass on to the poor countries or undeveloped countries as scrap. The scrape utilization and its mode of disposal are one of the main sources of the carbon and particulate matter in aquatic, aerial media and solid (solid media-soil). These media are the sites (natural laboratories) for synthesis, inter-conversion of living matter into nonliving matter and vice-versa where ecological and other cycles occur in nature. There pollutants interfere with these interconversions and hinder the balancing act on nature. It is utmost essential to maintain these media that provide clean and healthy environment for all living being. An effort is made to evaluate the physicochemical features; behavior and their prime impacts are discussed. released.

KEYWORDS: Behavior, Black carbon, brown carbon, hydrothermal vent, hydrophobic nature, physicochemical features of carbon particles, size-based carbon particles; immune system, formed components of blood.

PRELUDE

In our environment many pollutants are added every moment in one or other part of earth. Although, these are the products of natural calamities but quite good numbers of pollutants are the result of anthropogenic constructive or destructive activities. In most cases, the carbon particles are the products of combustion and the industrial processes. The terms like carbon particles (smoke/soot) and black carbon seem to be similar to a common man. These two entities are different in physicochemical sense. Soot and smoke are the formed as a result of incomplete combustion or fire and primary component is carbon related matter. The carbon black is the product of specific manufacturing process under controlled conditions. These are of industrial utility like ink and printing, dyes, paint and pigments etc. While

smoke is a mixture of carbon particles and impurities, contaminants along with carbon; this is because of the combustion of fossil-based fuels and biomass, smoking plant materials (like tobacco, herbal used for sedation or as habitual dependence), Very often cennosphere/cenosohere are also observed in smoke; cennosphere are the product of coal combustion in thermal power plants. These have light weight, inert, low density, high strength, hollow ceramic spheres basically made of silica, alumina and filled with air or inert gas/gases. These byproducts are used as fillers in concrete, polymers and plastics so as to reduce weight and elevate efficacy. The incomplete combustion is the primary source of poly aromatic hydrocarbons which are carcinogenic in nature. The process of atmospheric heterogenous oxidation play important role in changing

the composition of smoke/soot and adds to the obnoxious nature of smoke. There are possibilities of fluctuation in the composition of smoke and/or black carbon in atmosphere.^[1,2,3,4,5,6,7]

Carbon soot particles are the products of irregular fire, cooking, fire-wood, wood charcoal, any site or matter undergoing slow and incomplete combustion. Whatever the case may be, smoke and carbon-soot are the indicative sources of incomplete combustion and are the prime source of carbon particles pollution in environment. Good number of industries adopt combustion as one of the processes either for production or for destruction (step-up or step-down processes), including agricultural and industrial functioning. On fields or work place, the individuals use mask or cover their nose (respiratory entry port) to avoid the intake of carbon particles, but this preventive measure is not in practice when an individual faces smoke emitted from various sources, irrespective of land, air or sea routes and the quantity of smoke in atmosphere. Smoke is the common parameter since the advent of fire and still needs attention because of their presence in media and derogative behavior in the blood/body fluid of livestock, human being and other biota.

Combustion, complete or incomplete, is considered to be a step-down process as this helps to convert a complex organic matter in to its basic structural constituents. This process results in the emittance of smoke, soot, heat and light (solar) energy and 'absorbing components' in atmosphere. This emittance is potent enough to disturb the atmospheric equilibrium. Disturbed atmospheric condition causes uneasiness to the inhabiting biota therein. Thus, smoke (carbon soot particles) and organic carbonaceous materials present in the atmosphere, as aerosol, are obnoxious components. Hence, these become the targets to be investigated with respect to maintenance of pleasant, clean, healthy and suitable atmosphere for the biological components of an ecosystem. In the sense, the atmospheric pollutants are the prime parameters that affect and play major role in maintaining healthy ecosystem. Since, organisms are aquatic and terrestrial too, the pollutants in these media are also equally significant. Carbon particles are released as waste in pristine or combined form directly or through the gadgets used in printing industry, textiles, dyes and pigment, inks and paints industries like copier toner etc., in water or soil (earth). These additions disturb the macro, micro, meiofauna of these habitats.

Terms like black carbon, soot, elemental carbon, equivalent black carbon, and refractory black carbon and other components that have organic origin which become relevant with respect to heat-resistant and light-absorbing components in the atmosphere. These terminologies have specific definition and are measured using separate techniques. These become essential with respect to atmospheric and aquatic sciences (8-Petzold, 2013). Basically, the carbon particles are categorised as

refractive carbon particles and carbon black particles. Refractive carbon particles are formed during incomplete combustion of carbon containing organic matter while carbon black particles are specifically manufactured for specific purposes like dyes pigments, ink and printing etc. Refractory carbon particles have significant toxic matter while these toxins are mostly removed from carbon black particles. Mostly, refractive carbon particles cause respiratory and cardiovascular disorders, cancers, birth defects in offspring, and carbon are the causes of carcinogenic impacts once enter a biosystem. Refractive carbon particles have multiple industrial uses and carbon black have specific industrial applications like rubber, painting, printing industries.

There are standardized and advanced analytic techniques such as electronic microscopy, X-ray diffraction, Raman spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy, UV-Visible spectroscopy, fluoresce spectroscopy, size exclusion chromatography, interactions between soot and oxygen technique and thermogravimetric analysis in practice. Observations based on these techniques are helpful in illustrating their over impacts in biosystems (9-Arnal *et al.*, 2013). The microphysical features of soot particles appear to be complex and depend on their sources, process of formation and meteorological conditions such as direction and wind velocity, air temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure and stability depending on the day and night time and cloudiness. The physical properties of carbon particles pertain to their density, ability to sublimate, conductivity of electric current and solubility. One parameter of carbon particles in soot plays significant role in determining their age and structural morphology is 'fractal dimension' (D_f). This parameter facilitates to investigate the morphological aspects of aggregation and the modifications of soot. The aging factor that includes phase, core-shell morphology, compositional heterogeneity and mixing state. The related models to study these carbon entities have been developed incorporating 'fractal dimension' (D_f); these also combine with diverse metric concerning age of the soot particles, measuring their specific optical absorption, radiating forcing effects.^[10] Indue course of time, carbon particles, as aerosol gets affected in their physicochemical state. As a result, features like size, shape, morphology, composition and ability and state of mixing with other elements etc., get modified. These modifications are likely to render the original carbon particles changed drastically.^[10] The carbonaceous aerosol present in troposphere and consists of external and internal conglomerations of soot and other organic particulate matter. In most case, the sources of these carbon particles are multiple like combustion of fossil fuels and biomass. There is a difference between combustion and incineration; combustion may be complete or incomplete or partial and there is production of heat and light while incineration is practically complete and regulated combustion in an enclosed furnace with no or least waste.

NATURE AND PHYSICAL APPEARANCE OF SOOT

Soot may be considered under black carbon and brown carbon; both are the two primary components in aerosols. Their existence depends on the atmospheric climatic system. Their microphysicochemical aspects vary with diverse atmospheric environments like urban, forest zones, remote region. Although there has been research on their physical, chemical, size and their abilities of light behavior but still lot is desired. According to 'Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)' carbon soot particles are the product of combustion (mostly incomplete combustion) of carbonaceous matter (more or less organic matter) very rich in carbon and relatively very low proportion of other elements like

oxygen, hydrogen (present as carboxyl and phenolic groups/compounds). These particles have imperfect graphite configuration.^[11] Generally, soot particles are grouped as empirical, semiempirical, and detailed soot. Phenomenologically, soot particles are considered to be model unit for studies in current research scenario.^[12] The source and type of soot formation process are the prime factors in rendering soot its specific appearance and qualities. Soot is made up of many nanoparticles (carbon particles having the size range within nanoscale) belonging graphite and diamond which are disturbed in their arrangement. Soot appears to be amorphous powder like matter and considered as 'amorphous carbon'. Following table shows different soot and nature.

Sr. No.	Type of soot and its source	Nature, appearance, probable components,	References
1.	Normal soot, incomplete combustion	Amorphous carbon,	[12,13]
2.	Carbon soot, gas-phase	Mutagen, Polycyclic hydrocarbons (PAHs), carcinogenic (International Agency Of Research in Cancer)	[15]
3.	Soot from incomplete combustion of compounds like acetylene	Contains nanoparticles having size between 6nm to 30nm; exhibit good ability to be associated with metal oxide and mineral and one can have good coating of sulfuric acid.	[6,12]

Size of a carbon particle plays an important role during their interaction with living organism. While dealing with carbon soot particles, one must bear in mind the size aspect. During combustion of different materials smoke and soot are formed having different sizes of carbon particles. All sized particles may enter a biosystem during inhalation and ingestion and all of these do not interact within cell or epithelial tissues of the organism. Those which are not up-taken by cells or engulfed by phagocytes or natural killer cells (rapid response lymphocytes of innate immune system) are likely to be released during egestion via alimentary canal or expelled

as excreta, or it may get deposited in the tissue like respiratory organs like ducts /lungs /gills. Currently, we are concerning only carbon particles while air and water contaminants may possess other fine to coarse particles having various impacts. The sizing of particles depends on the mode of their formation and the efficiency of the process. Mill process can produce starch in to particle size ranging between 10 to 0.3 micron (μm , 10^{-6} m). By increasing the efficacy of milling the size of particles attained can be less than 0.1 μ (14). Following is the list of sizes of various forms of smoke particles based on.^[14]

Sr. No.	Name of the particle	Approximate Size of the particle
1.	Auto and car emission	1 to 150 μm
2.	Burning wood	0,2 to 3 μm
3.	Coal black dust	0.2 to 10 μm
4.	Coal dust	1 to 100 μm
5.	Coal fuel gas	0.08 to 0.2 μm
6.	Combustion	0.01 to 0.1 μm
7.	Combustion related to motor vehicles, wood burning, open burning, industrial processes	Up to 2,5 μm
8.	Copier toner	0.5 to 15 μm
9.	Corn starch	0.1 to 10 μm
10.	Oil smoke	0.03 to 1 μm
11.	Rosin smoke	0.01 to 1 μm
12.	Smoke from natural materials	0.01 to 0.1 μm
13.	Smoke from synthetic materials	1.0 to 50 μm
14.	Smouldering or flaming cooking oil	0.03 to 0.9 μm
15.	Tabaco smoke	0.001 to 4.0 μm

(1 micron= one millionth of meter/ 10^{-6} m/ 1000 micron)

In practice, generally, size of particles with range 250nm to 3 μm are most suitable for the cellular up-take.

Particles within this range readily undergo phagocytosis. The biomolecules like caveolin and clathrin help the process of endocytosis and particles within 120 to 150 nm are also up taken commonly. The process of mediated endocytosis ensures the absorption of the particles of around 200nm. Cells concerned with the internalization or cellular up take accomplish these functions by more than one mode depending on the physiological need of the organism.^[16,17,18,19,20,21]

SOURCES OF CARBON PARTICLES IN ECOSYSTEM

Mostly, incomplete combustion of biofuel, fossil fuel and biomass are the primary sources of carbon particles in ecosystem. This form of carbon is referred to as 'black carbon' in ecosystem and it is further enhanced due to anthropogenic and natural activities like burning of 'crop-waste' after harvest, forest fire, volcano eruption, war, exhaust from vehicle, aeroplane, space mission etc.,. These carbon particles are omnipresent and cause more harm to biosystems than benefit. These particles are the cause of varied types of health issues and facilitate senescence, (chart attached shows most common sources of black smoke emission,^[22]

Carbon particles get distributed in atmosphere from the site of combustion and is destined to be translocated to different places and also geographical zones. These particles remain suspended in air depending on temperature, humidity, wind speed, direction, air pressure, density of air and weather conditions. Although, the carbon particles appear to be inert but exhibit varied interactions with the components of ecosystems. These particles settle on the surfaces of any biotic and abiotic objects, like surfaces of leaves, buildings (coated and uncoated), and depending on the smoothness of surface. The adherence of carbon particles is relatively much less on the smooth surfaces than on the rough surfaces. This settling may be only of carbon particles or in conjugation with other particles. If these particles are not removed or the surfaces are protected, then these settled materials affect the surfaces physically too. This is so because of its nature to collect moisture (though hydrophobic but on adsorptive aggregation, the aggregates collect moisture) facilitate formation of biofilms, or after collecting dust becomes suitable for germination of seeds which land on it after or during wind and animal pollination. The growth of vegetation (may be scanty but it weakens the construction). These carbon-particles get settled on plants along with dust particles and block the stomata, thereby, interrupting the exchange

of gases through leaves and may obstruct the process of light reaction phase of photosynthesis along with the rate of respiration. Carbon particles in air also settle on the various parts of the herbaceous and nursery plants, possibly affecting their overall growth. The vehicular exhaust released is hot also thus, carbon particles and temperature both inflict unhealthy impacts on plants.^[22]

Carbon particles exhibit some peculiar physical features which influence their stay in atmospheric as pristine form in comparison to CO_2 . These particles are able to absorb heat for solar radiations and add to the temperature of atmosphere. The carbon particles also reflect some proportion of incident solar radiation. When mixed with snow it increases the temperature. Thus, there are distinct role of black carbon particles influencing the climate and air. These also affects rain, cloud pattern, melting of snow and glaciers and they add to global ecological crises. The carbon particles derogatively impact plant physiology and hinder the solar radiation. Overall, these influence plant growth, nutrition, and real vegetative survival in an ecosystem. Carbon particles contribute grossly to air pollution. This in turn is cause of long term respiratory and cardiovascular complications in biosystems and lead to reduction of life-span by elevating the rate of senescence.

These particulate components affect induce premature demises in young ones because of the induction of 'acute lower respiratory infection leading to bronchitis, pneumonia and cardiovascular disorders. Other health complications like asthma, reduced lung functions, adverse effect during pregnancy that may lead to disorganised embryonic/fatal development and neurological issues in most of the vertebrates.^[22]

STRUCTURE AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON PARTICLES

Combustion and any process involving high temperature involving organic matter result in carbon soot particles. These particles exhibit solid and porous nature depending on the material and the process involved in formation. These are the components of aerosol which are very fine particulate matter ranging from micro to nano size. These particles are present either as single or fractal-aggregates (cluster of smaller monomers). These aggregates are similar, regular and/or irregular appear as tree branching or plume of smoke. The monomers have distinct morphology, mass and exhibit specific natural behavior and engineered system or set-up. These particles bring forth the origin and concept of particulate matter.^[23] It appears to be logical to review the physicochemical properties of carbon particles for better understanding of their mechanism of interactions in aqueous, areal media and also within a biosystem. The carbon particles exhibit some peculiar properties like physical features and composition, hygroscopic aspects etc. The term 'carbon' encompasses wide variety of materials including heteroelements like hydrogen, oxygen, sulfur, phosphorus etc. The term 'black carbon particles' are the products of combustions of carbonaceous matter and these form gaseous phase. The process of decomposition or incomplete combustion are the primary mode of their formation. The black carbon consists of thousands of pseudospherical ultra small particles. The size of the black carbon spherical particles varies between 10 to 40 nm.^[24] The primary soot particles are solid in nature.^[23] The carbon soot particles show microstructure that resemble the reduced graphene oxide with oxygen-functional-groups with carbonaceous core; these have central core (CC) and outer coating of different materials. This conformational entity renders the soot carbon particles to render toxic impacts like oxidative stress, inflammation and damage of DNA. Generally, central core appears to be oil-rich zone-graphene-like and the outer coating consists of aromatic compounds associated with either two or more benzene rings. This conformation of carbon soot particles ensures their reactivities and unpleasant impacts on health. The hygroscopic efficacy of carbon soot particles is in relation to its ability to associate with water soluble materials and organic carbon. This efficacy gets elevated with the formation of sulfate because of heterogenous oxidation of SO₂. Basically, the impacts of carbon soot particles on the health of a biosystem depends on the mode of combustion and degree of reduction in emission form the soot.^[25]

The structure of the carbon soot particles changes with the conditions or source of soot formation. With rise of temperature of their medium, there is a decay or dissociation because the vibrational movements increase. As the impact of temperature increase it affects the dissociation forces in a given molecular structure. This process initiates at the molecular level. The vibrational movements together with dissociation forces and binding energy of the atom undergo changes and are different at different sampling locations. Each particles have specific thermal threshold stability but during oxidation process the scenario is different.^[26] The physical features of carbon soot particles are likely to vary depending on the sources for their formation. In general, approximately the average size of primary carbon soot particles varies between 15nm to 170nm and the common shape of single particles seems to be roughly spherical.^[26] The overall functional and structural concepts of black carbon soot can be converged as: in an aerial component of aerosol, it exhibits an intense visible light absorption and it is around 5m² /g at 550nm and it is quite uniform across the spectrum. These particles have unique nature of refractory-ability, to withstand higher temperature and harsh chemical reactive impact. These particles are generally used as lining of the furnace which operate at high temperatures (around 4000 K). These particles exhibit aggregated morphology and these are insoluble in water but dissolve in concentrated sulfuric acid. This feature may help in its application in multiple industrial utilities.^[27,28]

Carbon exists in allotropic forms and this is because of its tetravalency state. Most common allotropic forms are diamond and graphite. The allotropic forms of carbon are fullerene (a Buckminster fullerene- a ball like nano scaled) and sheet shaped, the graphene, nano forms of carbon like nano tubes, nano buds, nano ribbons, nano-ions etc.,^[21] According to Samara Carbon Allotrope Database presently, around 500 hypothetical 3-periodic allotropes are reported. There are unusual allotropes which tolerate very high temperature and extreme pressure.^[29] Diamond and graphite do exist as lattice form while other do not. Fullerenes (enclosed cage having nano scale), carbon nano tubes do not have lattice form. These carbon allotropes are the result of adaptability of different types of binding.^[30] Coal and soot particles both have crystal lattice configuration but different from each other. In coal the crystal lattice is well organized but in most of the lattice in soot is not organized. If the crystalline lattice in soot is graphitized (well organized) is considered to be natural fuel. The graphitized lattice in soot seems to be polyhedron; the surface with crystallized soot has basic planes placed as parallel arrangement. These layers are well organized in graphite crystal lattice than in the soot particles. One can observe 100 to 200 carbon atoms and 2 to 10 such plates whose thickness varies between 1.0 to 3.0nm in an elementary crystallite (electron microscopy). A spherical soot particle having diameter ranging 20 to 30nm contains 103 to 104 crystallites. The effect of high

temperature above 1000°C, these nanostructures exhibit elevated diameter and height and above 2800°C temperature initiates the process of graphitization resulting in setting the rearrangement of the crystalline lattice. There is every chance that spherical individual soot particle and the aggregated particles growth of the surface take place. The source and mode of formation of carbon soot particles play a major role in their morphology. Like diesel soot tends to form conglomerates having some hundred to thousands of spherical and nanosized soot particles.^[26]

The microphysical features of carbon soot particles play significant role in their interactions within the ambient air and aquatic media. The fractal (geometrical or curved compositional components) dimensions of carbon soot particles are helpful in quantifying their morphology, phase, aging phenomenon, degree of soot aggregation, and internal mixing ability, core-shell conformation, structural aspects of heterogeneity. Recently, the research related to development of fractal dimension, and mixing ability of aged carbon soot particles has been undertaken and as a result their assessment based on their optical absorption and radiative forcing effects has evolve. The microphysical features of these carbon soot particles depend on the source of these particles, aging process and meteorological conditions existing in the specific zone of ecosystem. Mostly, soluble organic particles are present in different forms and readily participate in liquid-liquid phase separation using sulfate and nitrate constituents. The primary carbonaceous particles like tarballs and soot carbon particles are the prime research target because these entities are small, possess prominent light absorbing properties, contain strong toxic constituents and are the sources of ailment to the biosystems.^[31] Pure fullerene (an allotropic form) with nano sized nanoparticle is insoluble in water and aggregates forming suspension; its interaction in water depends on its surface properties, spatial and dynamics. It is very useful in research field, because it can form water soluble derivatives. Its impact may be either toxic, neutral or useful during its interaction within biosystem. Fullerene along with its derivatives show ability to scavenge and form ROS, RNS (reactive nitrogen species), as an imaging agent, antiviral and antimicrobial efficacy.^[32] Traditionally and primarily, soot carbon particles are one of the clinically disapproved areal pollutants. These are associated with human since the advent of fire. In recent times, these carbon soot particles have been one of the useful and important materials. These particles are quite suitable for electricity storage, catalytic interactions, electronic field, detoxification of water and or water remediation, etc. Their interactions depend on parameters such as pH, duration of contact or exposure and concentration, at least far water remediation.^[33]

With reference to oceanic interaction with black carbon soot particles, the deep-sea hydrothermal vents appear to be the probable sites or sources of thermogenic dissolved

black carbon in aquatic medium. These carbon particles are one of the obstinate and more or less non-reactive addendum as dissolved/suspended organic carbon in marine and freshwater ecosystems. The origin of carbon particles can be from decomposition of organic matter, hydrothermal action of existing marine hydrothermal vent. Other sources of dissolved/suspended black carbon may be volcanic eruptions, fire and discharge of fossil fuel either accidentally or naturally. There seems to be less research related to hydrothermal (thermogenic) dissolved carbon in marine ecosystem at different depths of ocean. Possibly various “marine hydrothermal vent” may add to the interaction between carbon particles and sea water. There appears to be mixed opinion regarding the relationship between ‘apparent oxygen utilization’ and ‘thermogenic dissolved carbon’ or simply ‘dissolved black carbon’ in marine ecosystem. There is greater possibility of distribution of dissolved black carbon in the marine ecosystem because of the temperature difference between the region of hydrothermal vent the region far away from it. Another possibility can be the translocation of deep-sea water in the ocean because of hydrothermal system.^[34] The fresh water ecosystem is also affected because it receives industrial discharge (hot and cold both) and waste from various industries (treated or untreated and legally or ill-legally) may also add to the contamination.

SURFACE CHARGE ON THE CARBON SOOT PARTICLES

Carbon soot particles are produced as a result of combustion possess specific electrostatic charge and electrostatic potential. They have -ve, +ve charge and neutral and have electrostatic potential. The carbon soot particles are the result of flames or combustion engines or ions through chemiionization. The basic concepts of electrostatic charge include bipolar distribution, charge flames, engine exhaust. These features have significant applications during their interactions. Most of the carbon soot particles are charged 100%, at least those produced by engine exhaust but significant percentage of them are electrostatically neutral. There are reports on carbon soot particles about their electrostatic features. The charging mechanism of soot particles is due to their linking with ions formed during combustion (chemi-ions), thermal emission of electrons (thermionic emission) and the charge transfer from the surrounding. Soot aerosols are electrically charged mostly because of the 60 to 90 % exhaust particles are charged but at the same time, the aerosol as a whole appear to be neutral (balanced mix of +ve and -ve charge). The presence of electrical charge affects the growth and formation of soot. Strong electrical or magnetic field, can be used to manipulate, remove, or even reduce the size of particle which control their trajectories. The repulsive forces between the charge particles have tendency to slow down the rate of aggregation or coagulation as these soot particles age and aggregate. The process of aging and maturing of soot particles the electrical conductivity of these particles varies. Their conductivity significantly enhances with the

height above the burner or site of combustion. The presence of electrical charge affects the formation and growth of the soot particles. An application of strong field is able to manipulate, remove, or even reduce the size of particle as their trajectory changes. There is a specific charge on the soot (carbon) particles when these are in flame.^[35]

EFFECTS OF pH ON CARBON SOOT PARTICLES

The pH of the medium exhibit significant impacts on carbon soot particles. The colloidal carbon particles are sensitive to the changes of pH of the media and exhibit change in their inter active behaviour.^[36] This parameter changes the nature of the physicochemical reactivity of these particles. The hygroscopic tendency, chemical properties and their utility of these particles fluctuate with the change of pH of its medium as a result, their interaction with water also changes.^[37] All most all fluids have either specific pH or a set variable range of pH narrow range more so the biological fluids. The pH of atmosphere (aerosol) is a functional parameter of climatology influencing the functionality of the aerosol more so the soot particles present therein. Currently, the range of climatic pH of the aerosol is approximately is highly acidic i.e., pH ~ 0–3.^[38] The suspended solid and liquid particles are some of the main components of aerosol in a given location, urban or rural, industrial or war zone etc. The aerosol is the prime environmental condition that plays a significant role in the health of the biota of the ecosystem. Size of the particulate matter is a deciding factor that the given particles can be up-taken by epithelial lining of the organs of biota. Mostly, less than 2.5 µm sized particles and particles less than 100nm are able to pass through the biological barriers present in a biosystem and reach the body fluid or blood.^[39] The body fluids become the site of interaction between these particulate entrants and the various biomolecules and specific cells like phagocytes, killer cells and other cells concerned with immunological responses. In this context the physicochemical behaviour of the particulate matter is of paramount significant. These may be affected by solar radiation, atmospheric temperature, pH and the type of the solar radiation in air born phase. In the field of climatology, the role of aerosol and its interaction with aerosol radiation and aerosol-cloud-radiation interactions may result in drastic fluctuations in the aerosol and climate. Aerosol carries with it particles of diverse nature like soot particles, sulfate, nitrates, and many organic components having ammonia and other components.^[35,38,40] Studies reveal that carbonaceous aerosol inflict most of the toxic impacts. These are formed due to domestic cooking, activities related to disposal and burning of agricultural waste.^[38] Basic and mostly accepted view of carbon and other particulate matter is in relation to oxidative stress in epithelial cells, acidity-driven metal dissolution and secondary organic aerosol particles.^[38]

The hygroscopicity plays an essential role during the interaction between water and carbon soot particles. This

interaction helps to classify the soot carbon particles based on gravimetric measurements, analysis of chemical composition and porosity. Based on the 'humidified tandem differential mobility analyser' one can study the growth pattern in relation to relative humidity for quasi-monodisperse particles. The ability of the carbon soot particles is based on their ability to uptake water and surface polarity. It is observed that laboratory carbon soot particles exhibit varying degree of hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity. Possibly, the thermal carbon soot particles are hydrophobic and have low surface polarity. This feature is the basis for presence of water only on the half surface of the soot particles. The soot particles produced by heating/combustion of graphitized matter show very high degree of hydrophobicity as there is least surface polarity. On combustion the TC1, an aviation kerosene, forms carbon soot particles which are less hydrophobic and their complete surface is covered with water. These soot particles exhibit limited peripheral porosity and these particles grow up to 1.07 at relative humidity higher than 80%. These particles possess irreversible growth (swelling) due to up-take of water. This feature is based on the 'hysteresis (tendency in which the value of a physical property lags behind changes in the effect causing it) of adsorption' (up-take process) and desorption (release process) concept. It appears that the hygroscopic, hydrophilic and hydrophobic properties of carbon soot particles are related to the source used for combustion involved in their production. This feature also depends on the nature of the material that interact with them in a given medium. Thus, the interacting ability of carbon soot particles and the ambient medium are significantly involved in the process.^[41]

SOLUBILITY OF CARBON PARTICLES (HYDROPHOBIC NATURE)

Generally, pristine carbon particles are hydrophobic in nature and form suspension but not a solution. This behaviour is because of their nonpolar nature. The distribution of charge is depended on mode of formation and other inter actions with the contents of aerosol, aging and aggregation. Once they get chemically modified with hydrophilic groups these behave like a water-soluble material and exhibit variable solubility depending on its interaction with hydrophilic group. In atmosphere, as aerosol, carbon soot particles interact and shows apparent degree of solubility. The hydrophilic nature of carbon is due to its non-polar nature. It is a nonmetal element and uniform distribution of charge and it possibly, relate with its behavior with hydrophilic group or component of aerosol. Thus, the solubility of carbon soot particles is not an independent feature. The insoluble ability is based on presence of carbon-carbon and carbon-hydrogen bonds. One may assume that carbon soot particles exhibit very low solubility in water and their propensity to aggregate when subjected to nonpolar ambient neighbourhood that play a significant role during their interaction in aqueous medium.^[42] Generally, the hydrophobic feature of a

molecules/compound acts as a basic functional force during chemical and biological interactions like recognition of molecules, folding of proteins, interaction with biological membranes, macromolecular complexes formation, surfactant aggregation, complex formation during coagulation, detergency, formation of micelles and the stability of these entities, in aqueous media.^[43,44,45,46,47] The empirical calculation of partition coefficient (log-P) is the basis of expressing the hydrophobic nature of a given compound while designing a drug, medicinal chemistry and pharmacokinetics.^[48,49]

Fate of nanosized particles in environment is very significant aspect as these entities enter and affects biosystems either directly or indirectly. These particles include volatile compounds, dissolved ions and/or compounds, molecular species, biopolymers, natural organic matter, natural nano particles, coated natural nano particles, synthetic matter, anthropogenic nanoparticles and other contributions. These particles are distributed in air, water and sediment/soil. These can undergo physical fragmentation due to effects of climatic or weathering impacts. Some of these particles also exhibit sorption, aggregation, evaporation and transported as aerosol. In living organisms these particles undergo bioaccumulation, biomagnification, bioaggregation, biodistribution in various system of the biosystem. In aquatic medium they may remain suspend or settle to bottom and add to sediment.^[50]

BEHAVIOURAL ASPECTS OF NANO SIZED CARBON AND OTHER PARTICLES IN BIOSYSTEM

All biosystems inhale atmospheric soot and brown smoke via respiratory rout and these inflict harmful effects. Quite often, solid carbon also gets ingested along with over cooked, over roasted and burnt food. It is

evident that larger carbon particles pass out along with excreta as unaffected by enzymatic actions, while some having very fine size may find entry to blood vascular system via capillaries of wall of alimentary canal and lungs. These fine carbon particles may not react with biomolecules intensely and immediately but offer some sort of rheological interference to the flow of blood.^[21]

Generally, carbon soot is one of the major pollutants in the ecosystem and is known to affect adversely the biosystems. It is investigated that this so-called pollutant can be of functional utility. Carbon soot possesses some of the specific physicochemical features that make them more applicable in the fields of energy storage, chemical catalysis, electronics, writing, printing and preserving information, water treatment etc. The parameters like solubility, pH of the medium, duration of contact, concentration, surface charge and temperature play significant role in domestic, industrial and remedial processes.

Carbon soot particles in atmosphere or in aquatic medium reach biosystem either through inhalation (respiration) and ingestion (over cooked, roasted, smoked, burnt during cooking or accompanied long with food). These unwanted entrants are known to induce inflammation and defective impacts on cardiovascular system. The carbon particles of selective sizes enter in biosystem as particulate matter and access the blood stream via epithelial cells present as ling of respiratory surfaces and alimentary canal. The cell membrane of epithelial cells and these fine carbon particles interact and pass through this biological barrier. On reaching blood stream these circulate along with blood and reach all most all organs of the biosystem. It is understandable that after carbon soot particles enter blood stream these exhibit their impacts of blood tissue and get translocated to various systems of the organisms.

Overall, some common derogative impacts of carbon soot particles in an individual may be summarized as follow:

The broad view of recommended mechanism involved during the interactions of carbon soot (products of combustion of organic matter and diesel exhaust) and carbon black particles (printex-90). Theoretically, these toxic interactions can be sequenced in two modes, namely, direct mode of toxicity (localized) and inflicting systemic (toxic impact).

DIRECT/LOCALIZED MODE OF TOXIC IMPACT

DIRECT CONTACT WITH EPITHELIAL CELLS, INTERACT WITH MITOCHONDRIA AND UP-REGULATE CELLULAR INFLUX OF Ca IONS; INDUCTION OF CELLULAR OXIDATIVE STRESS AND INDUCTION OF CELLULAR SURVIVAL AND DEATH RESPONSE FOLLOWED BY INITIATION OF AUTOPHAGY AND APOPTOSIS; MAY LEAD TO CANCER BY INTERRUPTING CELLULAR AUTOPHAGY AND APOPTOSIS; CAUSES METHYLATION OF DNA AND ITS ADDUCTS FORMATION; ACTIVATION OF ARYL HYDROCARBON RECEPTOR; CAUSE DNA BREAKS, DERAILED DNA REPAIR MECHANISM ENSURING CANCEROUS CONDITIONS

SYSTEMIC MODE OF TOXIC IMPACT

INDUCTION OF CELLULAR INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE IN LUNGS AND EPITHELIAL TISSUE CAUSING INFLAMMATION; INITIATION OF CELLULAR SECRETION OF INFLAMMATORY MEDIATORS LIKE CHEMOKINE AND CYTOKINES THAT ENHANCE IMMUNE RESPONSE; PROMOTE PRODUCTION OF CELLULAR INTERLEUKIN-13 AND TRANSFORMATION OF GROWTH FACTOR BETA TO ACTIVATE FIBROBLAST CELLS TO ENSURE PRODUCTION AND ACCUMULATION OF EXTRACELLULAR FIBROUS PROTEINS; EXISTING MONOCYTES AND MACROPHAGES PRODUCE MORE METALLOPROTEASES AND TOXIC MEDIATORS TO ALTER THE PHYSIOLOGY OF BRAIN AND CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM; PRODUCTION OF SERUM AMYLOID TO CAUSE HEPATIC AND RENAL COMPLICATIONS;

Even the areal particulate matter affects the normal physiology and functionality in a biosystem. Their impacts are dependent on the duration, size and concentration/dose. Under higher concentration the symptoms appear very fast but low concentrations of particulate matter it takes time. Normally, there are morphological changes in erythrocytes due to physiological dysfunctions, nutritional deficiency, alcoholic habits. The particulate matters induce good number of such changes in erythrocytes that vary from echinocyte to stomatocyte forms. The nitration between particulate matter and erythrocyte causes their membrane to rupture. These conditions of RBC correlate with the dose and duration of exposure.^[51,52] Normally, the carbon soot particles and the carbon black (printex-90) after reaching blood stream and subsequently on reaching the organs have potential to induce oxidative stress, cardiovascular disorder, increased heart rate, pulmonary, reproductive dysfunctions, Further, promote cancerous growth and elevation of blood pressure are the probable, after effects of these particles.

INTERACTION BETWEEN NANO-SIZED CARBON AND OTHER PARTICULATE MATTER WITH IMMUNE SYSTEM

Immune system is the primarily concerned with the defence of the organism from its invaders. These invaders may be xenobiotics and endogenous. Immune system operates as two subunits namely innate and specialized or acquired/adaptive in nature. The immune system has two functional components, cellular and humoral. Cellular component includes cells like

lymphocytes, phagocytes, leucocytes, platelets, killer cells, immune cells while the humoral part carry-out its function with its functional components present as humoral components (fluid and biomolecular part). The immune system functions very precise and in specific manner. Both units function independently and govern the 'response' to the obnoxious stimuli. Its limits of adaptability are fairly good to provide suitable and effectual responses. Immune system in a biosystem is dedicated to protect it from external as well as endogenous harmful entities or biomolecules that invade the body of an organism or formed as result of dysfunctioning of molecular pathways. Since, the body of the one organism is food for the other according to the 'energy pyramid' and 'food chain' concept. Any organism will try to thrive on whatever these can derive nutrition from available matter and ability to consume it. The pathogens like fungi, bacteria, viruses etc., will invade the any suitable host they can infest. In this category even the air and water born particulate matter (natural and anthropogenic) both have capacity to invade the susceptible host. The immune system plays its role in avoiding these biological and non-biological invaders. So, its basic function is to identify and destroy the invading such entities and neutralize their impacts. Some of these can be senescent cells, damaged or structurally and functionally abnormal endogenous entities. These entities can be cellular and biomolecular in nature. The components of immune system are able to detect and eliminate such structures even if they are nano scaled. Even the entities like molecularly abnormal, dysfunctional, and interfering with the metabolic

mechanisms are identified and either destroyed or discarded for the biosystem. The biochemical components of invading biomolecules like proteins, nucleic acid sequences and additionally formed biomolecules, all such entities enter the scrutiny of immune system. The components of immune system identify, detect, carbon soot and carbon black particles along with their components and undergo the defensive mechanisms i.e., either inflammatory or anti-inflammatory responses.^[53,54]

The interactions between carbon soot and carbon black particles along with other particulate matter exhibit short term, long term, acute and chronic dose result in responses in accordance to the dose, type and nature of the particles and the target individual. In laboratory, test animals are tested the respective responses and limits of toxicity. Humans are no exception to these investigations. All these investigations are helpful to understand the efficacy and mechanism involved the functioning of immune system. Further investigations in this direction will enhance the understanding of roles of various components (humoral and cellular) of immune system and will enrich our remedial limits of pharmacological field.^[55]

The cellular components like, macrophages, neutrophils, T-lymphocytes and β -lymphocytes, eosinophils, basophils, mast cells, dendritic and natural killing cells of immune system play very important role in the processes of delivering immune responses. Hence, their role should be understood for better understanding and remedial purposes. Their physicochemical and functionalities are of clinical significance. These cellular components exhibit series of process like activation, action and disposing the inactivated pathogen or xenobiotics. Phagocytosis, endocytosis, exocytosis are the functional aspects of these cells.^[55]

Phagocytes have specific receptors present on their membrane which receive signals from neutrophils and macrophages. These identify the targeted particles or xenobiotic and after being activated react to the respective toxicity. The physicochemical features of the invader play important role in this interaction. Such interactions are based on the surface features of the invader (its -ve or +ve membrane charge and other surface properties) ensure the cellular up-take of these xenobiotics. The charged xenobiotics enter phagocytes readily as compared to those having neutral or no charge. After activation, the macrophages actively uptake (engulf) nano sized particles clear them from the body. Among vertebrates specific endogenous molecules play significant role in identification of any 'pattern', 'pathogen' and 'danger-associated pattern'; these are termed as 'alarmins'.^[56] The effector cells belonging to the innate adaptive immunity and are helpful in cellular communication. In most cases during cellular activation three prime biomolecules play significant role and they are -'pattern recognition receptors' (PRRs), 'primary-

pathogen associated molecular patterns' (PAMPs) and 'danger-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). These molecules help the cells to sense the level of danger at cytomolecular level. The efficacy of phagocytes depends on the pre-stimulation of lipopolysaccharide -a primary-pathogen associated pattern-formation.^[57,58] Although the number of neutrophils increases during the interaction indicating the level of inflammation but of the mechanism of activation of neutrophil is obscure. This process of activation is not distinctly understood and the pathological impacts of xenobiotics. It is considered that the innate immune response is expressed as inflammatory response, a basic defensive response and it may not be the indication of onset of pathological indication.^[59]

To xenobiotics; specifically, these cells exhibit higher degree of cellular plasticity. Cellular plasticity is an ability change their forms, functions, and identity in response to the inter and intra cellular signals. Such cells play major role during development, tissue repair, and regeneration. These cells have their significance during metastasis, treatment resistance, cell-differentiation, reprogramming etc. Thus, macrophages are known for their homeostatic role in an organism and function independent of the innate immunity.^[55,60] Generally, cellular debris are the result of either stress or tissues trauma. The endogenous danger signals like danger-associated molecular pattern (DAMPs), this includes nuclear proteins, heat shock protein, histones and nucleic acids.^[56] Receptors like 'pattern recognising receptors' (intra cellular) and receptor IL- help macrophages to identify 'danger-associated-molecular patterns'. The cell surface proteins undergo changes which facilitate the process of endocytosis and introduces mediators and inflammatory cytokines.^[60]

Generally, macrophages should be grouped as 'classically activated macrophages (M1) and alternatively activated (M2); since, macrophages exhibit varied forms of physiological and biochemical variations and these may create confusion. Mostly, when there is an elevated secretion of inflammatory mediators M1 form of macrophages increase in number. These also increase in number under the influence of cytokines interferon- γ and TNF- α . With reference to tissue, during early phases the innate immune response produces interferon- γ because of neutral killer cells and it results in the formation of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species. The macrophages have potential to damage tissue as these induce the production of IL-1 β , IL-6 and IL-23; these expands the T-helper-17 lymphocytes which in turn secretion of IL-17 and this induces involvement of neutrophil that damages the tissue. Basophils and mast cells help in production of IL-4 which follow injury of tissue and early secretion of IL-4 activate more of macrophages (alternative activated macrophages) which facilitate extracellular matrix and healing process.^[55, 61] Polarization in macrophages may or may affect interaction with nano particles and promote endocytosis;

the corona formation on nano particles with proteins can influence this process.^[55,62,63] Macrophages translocate from blood stream to the tissues where they replenish the old macrophages (may be derived from embryo), here these macrophages are mononuclear phagocytes system and include osteoblast, microglial, alveolar cells, Kupffer's cells, spleen and gastrointestinal tract.^[64,65] The role of macrophages during the interaction actions with nano particles among all these varied population seems to be ambiguous.^[55]

Neutrophils also play a role of member of first line of defence and are present in relatively good numbers. These can be observed along with macrophages within tissue as tissue resident. Those nano particles who cross over the tissue barriers encounter these granulocytes. These blood cells cripple and isolate the invaded nanoparticles and result in the formation of granuloma.^[56] These cells are the subset of T-cells are the functional components in recognition of pathogen when inflammatory responses are delivered under autoimmune infection.^[66] In these cells the internalization of nano sized particles is in proportion to their size. When these granulocytes encounter exogenous and endogenous nano particles release 'danger-associated molecular receptors' as a result of 'neutrophil extracellular traps' 'NETS'; the process is called (NETOIS). This molecular development is in relation to the parameters like formation of reactive oxygen species, granular enzymes ('neutrophil esterase' and 'myeloperoxidase').^[67,68] The enzyme myeloperoxidase acts on the nano particles, more specifically engineered nano particles, thereby, reducing the toxic impacts. This aspect may be considered as protection which the innate immune system provides.^[69] During NETOIS process, the neutrophil extracellular traps are the result of disruption of membrane and both enzymes ('neutrophil esterase' and 'myeloperoxidase') translocate in the nucleus. There these starts degrading histone, followed by decondensation and chromatin and granular proteins become free. The intensity of NETOIS process depends of the size of nano particles, rate of damage of plasma membrane and membrane of lysosomes and stability of membrane. The overall severity of this process variety of nano particles. In case of carbon or polystyrene nano particles depends on their size.^[69,70]

Dendritic cells are associated with innate and adaptive immunity as a messenger. These are spherical but develop dendrites (branching) as per the need arises. In case of immature stage of dendritic cells their surface is covered with very fine folded sheet-like structures, looking like veil-'veiled cells' while at maturity these appear like branching of a tree, hence, dendritic cells. Mostly dendritic cells are observed on the surface of T-cells and primarily concerned with the processing of antigen.^[71] Dendritic cells are present within the tissues and blood. These cells are seen in the tissues that are linked with the external environment like skin of the body of an organism. These are also seen along with the

nasal lining, lungs and gastric as well as intestinal linings. In blood, these are present as immature and matured states. But after activation these migrate to the lymph nodes. In these nodes they interact with T-cells and B-cells. Morphologically, these cells have very large to volume to surface ratio due to their folds (veil like) present at their surface.

The dendritic cells develop from the hemopoietic bone marrow progenitor cells also called 'hemopoietic stem cells'. The progenitor cells metamorphose into immature dendritic cells; these cells exhibit endocytosis of higher rate but cell activation is less. The mature dendritic cells search for pathogen such as bacteria and viruses. These cells identify the pathogen with help of 'pattern recognition receptors' like 'toll-like receptors'. Biochemically these receptors at molecular level accept the chemical signature of the antigen (microbe) either in part or completely. Dendrite cell exhibits nibbling of its own membrane. On activation dendrites reach lymph nodes. At maturity the dendritic cells gain an ability to recognise the units of innate immune system such as antigen, 'pathogen-associated molecular pattern', 'danger-associated molecular pattern and loose the efficiency of phagocytosis and identify phagocytic receptors. Thereafter, they gain access to lymphoid tissues. Investigations in mice show that their life span to be around 10 to 14 days in spleen. Around 4000 thousand cells get replenished in an hour and these cells show limited times of cell division in spleen.^[72] The ability of degree of recognition of physicochemical features of nano particles or their coating or surface properties by dendritic cell and involvement of the components of innate immune system is very essential to be understood. The processing of the antigen and its interaction with T-cells appears to be of significance in the field of pharmaceuticals and nano-medicine.^[55]

Natural killer cells or NK cells have capacity to kill the living cell or invader pathogen (natural killer cells), these cells also called cytotoxic cells and come under 'cytotoxic T-cells'. These cells come under lymphocytes type of cells and function as a cellular component of innate immune system. Morphologically these lymphocytes are granulated and referred to as 'innate lymphoid cells'. These cells form about 5-20% of the population of lymphocytes of circulation in an adult human.^[73,114] These cells play significant role during the process of adaptive immune response. The killer cells are functionally very active during viral infection, stress condition or cellular stress, tumor cell, during the intracellular signalling process of pathogen infection, during activation and functioning of inhibitory receptors. Their functioning relates with the presence of antigen either present in circulation or present on the other cells. These cells kill those cells which do not have a self-mark, generally harmful cells do not possess the self-mark.^[74] Bone marrow, lymph nodes, spleen, tonsils and thymus are the site of differentiation and maturation of NK cells. These cells have remarkable adaptability and

adjust in accordance to ambient environmental changes in antigen specific 'immunological memory' and to function against secondary infection if caused by same antigen.^[73,75,76,77] Since these cells attack the 'sick or affected cells', their action on cells affected with carbon nano particles or other type of nano particles should also be attacked by them.

Cronin *et al.*, 2020, show the participation of Natural killer cells during their interaction dark carbon particles, macrophages T-cells epithelial cells and endothelial cells even though their presence in blood stream their interaction is more evident in the affected tissues rather than blood. These entities are known for interacting with the destruction of stressed, infected with viruses, or showing abnormal activity.^[55] This process is accomplished through the direct antibody mediators 'death receptor path-way or involvement of TNF receptors; this function ends in the apoptosis of the attacked cell. In this process the activated NK cells deliver immune activating cytokines, like IFN- γ , IL-4 and TNF- α , these deal with dark carbon particles along with other invaders. The normal healthy cells do not get adversely affected by NK cells because of the 'major histocompatibility complex.^[78,79,80,81,82] Mostly NK cells are present in blood stream and on the mucosal cell surface these cells interact with nano particles readily. In all probability early exposure of nano particles or engineered nano particles face an innate immune response; in this interaction Ink cells participate and the involvement of T-cell appears to be the final step in the innate immune response.^[55]

Engineered nano sized particles react with the components of immune system and related biological components. Cellular components such as neutrophils, macrophages and other effector cells give induced to give inflammatory responses depending on the dose, the inflammation may be acute or chronic in accordance to the degree of exposure. The other cells of immune system like dendritic cells and 'primary antigen presenting cells' also participate in this process. The mechanism involved is not well understood, if related study undertaken then this aspect will elucidate the complexity of immune response and strategies of vaccination concept. The physical parameters of nanosized particles like size, shape and their deformability play significant role during the respective immune responses. Further, there are every chance of formation of corona occurring during the stay of these particles due their adsorption and these interactions cannot be ignored. The formation of corona may be helpful in regulating the interactions in order to the elimination/clearing these particles and safety for the biosystems.^[109]

INTERACTION BETWEEN CARBON PARTICLES AND PLATELETS

Current research scenario on the effects of exposure of carbon particles and particulate matter reflects the

activating activities of platelets and influences their von Willebrand functionalities. [Von Willbrand factor is responsible for the specific functions of platelets. This factor plays important role of glycoproteins in their ability of adhesion and hemostasis while in blood circulation. This is also important for blood clot formation. Von Willbrand factor acts as a functional link between platelets and the collagen present at the site of vascular damage). This factor links with glycoprotein-Ib present on the platelets and ensures their adhesion with blood vessel and starts the process of clotting, thus, ensuring the adhesion of platelets as per the need. The von Willbrand factor functions as a protector after it has binding with factor-VIII, and prevents its degradation while it is in circulation. This step also helps to maintain appropriate level of factor VIII so that coagulation cascade is maintained and thus, helps in maintaining specific level of hemostasis This factor mediates the process of aggregation of platelets and also facilitates its participation with collagen. The shear stress of the blood flow also activates this factor. This process also improves the ability of clot formation.^[83] The diesel exhaust particles also elevate the response of platelets to aggregation and mobilize Ca^{+2} , degranulation and expression of P-selectin; these factors facilitate activation of platelets with respect to physiopathological exposures. One can administer diesel exhaust particles in regularized dose in blood circulation by infusion and study their locations and behavior of these cells. One can use radio isotope to tag these carbon particles and investigate their behaviour. Repeated and prolonged exposure of diesel exhaust particles are likely to result in cardiovascular dysfunctioning, their physical interaction with platelets results in 'typical conventional agonist-mediated aggregation' of platelets. Another impact includes risk of thrombosis in the individual.^[84]

The ambient particulate matter affects the degree of coagulation (hyper, hypo coagulation) and thrombosis in vascular system. This impact is dependent on their size, concentration, type, nature, of the particulate matter.^[85] There are contradictory opinions about the correlation between von Willbrand factor and the concentration of particulate matter that causes the endothelial injury.^[86,87] Even the role of von Willbrand antigen is yet to be confirmed because there is very less effect of particulate matter on its function but the impact von Willbrand antigen is significant for short term exposure and it varies with the duration and the size of the particulate matter.^[62] The correlation between von Willbrand function and factor VIII is also significant, it becomes potentially significant with rise in concentration of particulate matter.^[88] There appears to exist some correlation between soluble P-selectin and the nanosized particulate matter, this interaction affects the activation of platelet.^[86,89] In a study on diabetic individuals there is report that the levels P-selectin and ADP were higher and resulted in induction of aggregation while the decline in collagen level, probably this factor enhance degree of aggregation along with formation of thromboxane B2 in

response to particulate matter.^[90] The instrument analyzer-100 (PFA-100) is a very helpful in study the functionality of platelets in response to the particulate matter. The impacts of particulate matter on the activation of platelets and/or aggregation. This instrument assesses the effect of anti-platelet agents and it can be possible that device is not suitable for observing the process of activation of platelets. There is possibility that the particulate matter affects the endothelial cells but not the platelets directly. One more possibility is that there is inborn tendency to maintain specific physiological functioning under the influence of invaders by involving some multiple mechanism. The technique of 'rotational thromboelastometry (ROTEM)' may be a better choice to investigate the various aspects like adhesion, expression of P-selectin and aggregation, interaction between particulate matter and platelets.^[91] There is great need to study the probable over all mechanisms concerning functionality and endothelial injury, aggregation and release of granules from platelets, levels of factors of coagulation, fibrinolytic set-up in an organism during their interaction with carbon particles, black carbon and other particulate matter. Such investigations are likely to show various varying observation in relation to climate, geographical zone, level of pollution, extent of burning fossil fuel, season, industrial conditions, sex, age and tolerance limits of the individuals.^[92,93,94,95]

The complement system is a humoral component of innate immune system and basically concerned with the identification, destruction and expulsion of the pathogens. First this system becomes activated and its cellular components then initiates its main function. Its basic principle is to interact with the protein coated foreign complex entities or pathogens like bacteria and viruses, enter a body. Particulate matter coated with protein are affected by this humoral immune component of innate immune system.

INTERACTION OF CARBON SOOT PARTICLES IN BLOOD OF A VERTEBRATE

The carbon soot particles are expected to interact with cellular components of blood like erythrocytes leucocytes, platelets, killer cells, immune cells etc. Other biomolecular blood components like proteins, (albumin, fibrin, globulin). There are direct impacts on the morphology of erythrocytes ranging from echinocyte to stomatocyte forms as a result of pathogenic, metabolic, nutritional disorder and deficiency. Generally, the cytomorphological aspects are ignored while reporting on the impacts of any interactions on the test animal. Relatively less references are available there on this aspect.

The carbon soot particles (diesel exhaust) and the carbon black (printex-90; B-100; B50) exhibit varied impacts on formed cellular components of blood. The common impact is the increase in the number of mean corpuscular volume, leucocytes, platelets, reticulocytes,

metamyelocytes, neutrophils, macrophages only degree of increase varies in carbon soot particles, diesel particles, carbon black (B-100; B50). Most of these cells relate with immune and/or immune response. This increase indicates the corresponding response of the individual in response to these carbon particles. All these carbon particles elevated the heart rate indicating their effects on cardiovascular function.^[7,96] This trend of the impact reflects that the carbon particles from diesel are relatively more toxic inducing inflammation and cardiovascular and pulmonary systemic functionality.

Kelsey and the team, reported on the genotoxicity of human cells due to areal particulate matter in the oil fields of Kuwait. This team reported on the peripheral blood lymphoblast cell line AHH-1. Apparently, the team did not mention about the cytomorphological aspects of erythrocytes (may seem to be outdated). The mutational and metabolic aspects of lymphocytes are reported as DNA adducts formation.^[97] The wood smoke particulate material lodged in gastric and pulmonary sites, on examination well advocated aspects like oxidative stress, inflammation, genotoxicity and DNA damage and consequently hepatic and pulmonary damages are reported. The dose of 0.64mg/kg body weight affected the metabolic functionality of liver as the levels of 8-oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-deoxyguanosine, 1,N⁶-etheno-2'-deoxyadenosine, and 1-N²-etheno-2'-deoxyguanosine increased. This observation is in correlation the quantity of dose. The intragastric and lung exposure results in elevation of 'hepatic genetic expressions of pro-inflammatory cytokines, heme oxygenase-1 and oxoguanine DNA glycosylase-1'; during similar exposure, the number of neutrophils in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid increased.^[98]

When whole BALB/C mice are exposed to +ve, -ve and neutral carbon soot particles for 7 days, their impacts are toxic impacts on pulmonary system and analysis proteomics. Of the three types of charged soot particles the +vely charged are more toxic than the -vely charged carbon and neutrally charged soot particles. The +ve charged carbon particles sized between approximately 69 to 72nm and with 1.17 to 1.35 electric charges inflict cytotoxic lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) and elevated rate of pulmonary permeability. As a result of this exposure, these +vely soot charged particles resulted in elevation of 8-prostane, caspase-3 and systemic interleukin (IL-6) in the pulmonary tissue. The +vely charged carbon soot particles also increase the functionality of Eif-2, Eif-4 (eukaryotic initiation factor that relates with translation initiation, impacts protein synthesis), sirtuins (a class of proteins and includes number of enzymes -sirtulin- term is a derivative of 'yeast gene silent mating-type information regulation), peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPAR) and pathways concerning HIPPO-related in pulmonary tissue (this signalling pathways are crucial for the cell-proliferation, size of an organ, development and regeneration of tissue). Further, these +vely charged soot particles increased quantitatively

the pulmonary HIF-1 α (a main transcriptional regulator concerning cellular and developmental response to hypoxia), sirt-1 (a protein that regulates inflammatory, metabolic disorders and cellular hypoxia), E-cadherin and YAP (a protein that regulates genes in a cell are turned on or off and a transcriptional coactivator). Thus, out of +ve, -ve and neutrally charged carbon soot particles the +vely charged ones are more toxic and are the concern with the health of biota in an ecosystem.^[7,99]

INTERACTION BETWEEN CARBON SOOT PARTICLES AND ERYTHROCYTES

The interactions between reactants are based on their physicochemical properties and the outcome may be either favorable, adverse or neutral. When carbon soot particles enter a biosystem they are bound to react and leave some impacts. These carbon soot particles cross-over the cellular histological barriers of the organs (in this case tissue of alimentary tract and pulmonary organs and reach the continuous flowing body fluids i.e., blood and from this fluid they reach lymphatic fluid, and interstitial fluids and finally cytoplasm. Throughout their journey they come across many types of cellular and biomolecular components of these respective fluids and in all possibility there will be some interactions between them. The blood is one of the targets/sites of interaction between the areal and aquatic pollutant entrants and the blood components.

As mentioned above, on exposure of carbon soot particles and carbon black find route to the blood stream. On the way to blood stream these particles act as active sources of inflammation, structural and functional disorganisation and damage to the tissues encounter enroute and the site i.e., blood. As a result, there is likely to be specific interaction between them and the blood components. These interactions are expressed as activation of cellular components of blood and the biomolecules existing therein. All these alter the normal structural and functional aspects of the blood tissue. One can expect rise in reactive species of oxygen, formation of proinflammatory cytokines, active involvement of adaptive immune system.^[54] In all probabilities, the macrophages activate their receptors present on their surface that identify and recognize the intruders in the vicinity i.e., intracellular space and fluid and the blood stream. This function is accomplished due to recognition of the intruder and the response is given accordingly. This process involves polarization of phenotype and macrophages and immune cells with respect to the intruder and produce 'opsonins' - a soluble molecules which facilitates the immune-response. Amid all these activities, the intruder molecules or particles reach their destination or spread throughout the organism. The macrophages have ability to identify and determine the probable impacts of the new entrant. These cellular components induce the intra and extra cellular signaling system involving cytokines, chemokines and initiate the formation of reactive oxygen species.^[51,54]

If hemolysis (any interaction that destroys red blood cells before their life span 120 days in humans), this feature varies in various vertebrates. It should not be considered to the only parameter for good health of blood in an individual. Such interactions depend on the dose, concentrations, duration, nature of the pollutants and the type of the organism. The cellular components of body fluid have specific osmotic fragility, limits of rheological abilities, and cellular structural aspects and the physicochemical of fluid and its vulnerability. It is very important to investigate the 'dose-response relationship'. The acute and chronic impacts in relation to the hyposensitive, normal and hypersensitive nature of biological entities^[100] In the context of blood cells carbon soot and carbon black first interaction appears to be with the cell membrane of erythrocytes. Their interaction with membrane is good indicator of vulnerability and susceptibility of erythrocytes towards carbon soot and carbon black particles. This interaction also reflects on the role of components and structural aspects of red blood cells such as glycocalyx, cell membrane and cytoskeleton. This may also exhibit their flexibility during their passage through very fine capillaries along with plasma.^[54,101,102,105,104]

Although carbon soot particles and carbon black particles may have same origin but carbon soot particles have more drastic derogative biological activity than the carbon black particles. These two products caused different health impacts.^[1] In an atmosphere there are refractory and normal carbon soot and carbon black particles both are different and impact biosystem in different manners. The refractive carbon soot particles and other form of carbon are one of the major solar light absorbers and are potent to affect radiative balance and also change the properties of clouds and global warming parameter. Such carbon particles exhibit specific morphology and density to mass ratio with the compactness and the shape of the particles. This ratio is significant with respect to climatic and health issues of biological specimens.^[105] Erythrocyte osmotic fragility test is one the most significant test to evaluate the erythrocytes membrane-carbon particles (pollutant) interactions to evaluate susceptibility, dysfunctions and vulnerability of erythrocytes with respect to the interaction with pollutant more specifically in blood. Hemolysis of erythrocytes represents the fragility, susceptibility and dysfunctionality of cells; this feature of erythrocytes represents the osmotic stress state in blood stream and as an impact of interaction with carbon particles. Since hemolysis release hemoglobin from cells on to the blood stream, estimation of hemoglobin before and after hemolysis will give the value of acute carbon particles the induces fragility, susceptibility and dysfunctionality limits with respect specific dose, and duration.^[54]

Synthetic and natural nanoparticles have potential to affect the parameters of blood cells and fluid part. The parameters include morphology, oxygen carrying

capacity, degree of coagulation, thrombosis, complementary activation, structural, functional fluctuation of membrane and their life-span of red blood cells. Further, these particles are able to induce some of the physicochemical fluctuations in functional features of blood/fluid, like viscosity, rheological aspects.^[106,107] There are more chances of the dimensional cellular fluctuations in erythrocytes and other cellular components of blood. Even, the polarity of red blood cells, the biomolecular components glycoproteins and glycolipids may be affected. There can be some deformations in the shape of the erythrocytes in correlation with spectrin cytoskeleton. These changes affect the mechanical and rheological parameters related to cellular components of blood.^[108,109]

INTERACTION BETWEEN CARBON PARTICLES AND PLASMA PROTEINS

Carbon nanoparticles/materials are used in industries like ink-printing, dyes and paints, textiles, metal industry, in biological and biomedical fields. This indicates vastness of their extent of utility and industrial production and consequently the release in eco system as waste. The released carbon particles get added to the atmosphere; all these add to the release of carbon particles in addition to combustion of fossil fuel and vehicular exhaust and other industrial release. These particles are being synthesized to meet the rising demands. Smoke and carbon particles are among the carcinogenic agents. Their molecular hemocompatibility is of great interest for pharmaceutical and remedial parameters. There is every possibility that black carbon, carbon element, and carbon black are present in carbon soot and this composition depends on the type and mode of sources of soot. The soot or black carbon are detrimental to health of biosystems more specifically to cardiovascular and pulmonary systems. These carbon particles have potential to induce structural detrimental issue to the proteins. Nano sized particles of carbon are present in air in varying quantity depending on the wind condition, geographical location, climate and use of combustible materials. Moreover, air is more or less heterogenous mixture of the various gases and very fine particles. The carbon particles enter in the body of all organisms during inhalation (respiration) and partly during ingestion (feeding and drinking). Being chemical in nature, these entrants are likely to interact with the body fluid and the contents present therein. These nano sized particles readily bind with protein contents of plasma of all vertebrates because of their physicochemical properties. The carbon particles form 'protein corona' as a result there is change in their surface properties and behaviour after these interactions. After the formation of protein corona their hydrated particle size and surface charge change. The formation of corona depends on the quantity of proteins present in the ambient medium. The most common proteins present in plasma are serum albumin, fibrinogen, globulin, apolipoprotein and immunoglobulin. These proteins vary in their structural, functional aspects and in quantities present in plasma. These proteins interact

electrostatically with carbon nanoparticles and cause the 'adsorption-induced structural fluctuations. The reported observation show that the protein corona formed in each case is different in comparison to the insoluble unreacted carbon particles during their existence in plasma/blood. As a result. their hydrological and behavioural interactions with formed elements like erythrocytes, leucocytes, platelets and other cellular contents also show variations and impact their toxicity limits.^[110]

The interactions with proteins are in relation to the degree of adsorption, equilibrium binding and conformational ability of proteins. These further depend on different functional aspects like association constant, binding cooperativity and secondary structural variations in proteins. Possibly, the dimensionality and surface area and density of the oxygenated functionalities of nano sized carbon particles also play significant role during these interactions. The dimensional investigations of carbon particles (synthetic and natural) may elucidate the mechanism involved physiological, biochemical, pharmaceutical and bio-applications.^[111] Carbon black particles with dimension lower than 2.5 μ m readily enter the pulmonary tissue; these particles react with surface proteins and lipids resulting in serious health damage and prove to be toxic. This interaction is observed using fluorescence quenching technique and UV-vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared and dichroism spectroscopies. The observations indicate that black carbon particles influenced the static quenching process and the role of hydrophobic force involved during their interaction with protein. These particles can cause slight changes in the folding of albumin but the secondary structure remained intact. With reference to cytotoxicity impacts, the low dose of black particles inflicted toxic effects on BEAS-2B cells (immortalized human bronchial epithelial cells derived from non-cancerous lung tissue) in comparison to the higher doses. It appears that bovine serum albumin (BSA) protected the tissue from the toxic effects of black carbon particles.^[112] Quite often there is an active interaction between ultrafine carbon particles and poly cyclic aromatic hydrocarbon. In the process compound like phenanthrene and pyrene bind with these particles. Thus, such compounds are liable to induce toxic impacts while interacting with human serum albumin and cytotoxic effects too. Such observations are readily recorded using transmission electron microscopy and isothermal titration calorimetry. Since, human serum albumin interacts well with dispersed carbon nano sized particles containing polycyclic hydrocarbon which in turn form bioconjugates involving hydrophobic forces. These bioconjugates bring about conformational and functionalities of the interacting proteins. The complexes are also the result of such reaction due to which the degree of toxicity gets lessened.^[113] Soot and carbon black particles induce metabolic processes like oxidative stress, methylation of DNA, DNA adduct formation, activation of aryl hydrocarbon receptors in a test animal which finally result in pathological conditions like cancer, respiratory

disease, cardiovascular disorders. In all, possibilities such impacts may be due to the added components like metals (Si, Fe, Mn, Ti and Co), halides (Cl⁻ and Br⁻) play significant roles in inducing various types of pathogenetic conditions. These impurities are the possible causes of activation of neutrophils and eosinophil, production of ROS that initiate the damage of DNA, formation of DNA adducts. These carbon particles along with their impurities have potential to trigger the pulmonary dendritic cells, T-helper cells, mast cells which mediate the onset of pulmonary pathological conditions. If polyunsaturated fatty acids are also present as impurities then these are the potential agents also facilitate intensify the severity of pulmonary diseases. Processes like 'telomerase reverse transcriptase' may also actuate and facilitate cardiovascular dysfunction.^[7] The carbon soot and carbon black particles form protein corona with primary plasma proteins like albumin, Fibrinogen, apolipoproteins A-1 and immunoglobulins. Their interaction with these proteins is likely to result in fluctuations in the secondary conformational changes. The primary cause of such effects seems to be the electrostatic interactions play role in the adsorption and in triggering conformational changes in these proteins.^[110,114]

CONCLUSION

Generally, carbon soot and carbon black particles are the major pollutants in the ecosystem and are known to affect adversely biosystems. These pollutants have the potentials to cause structural and functional physiological dysfunctions. Carbon soot and carbon black particles possesses some of the specific physicochemical features that make them more applicable in the fields of energy storage, chemical catalysis, electronics, writing, printing and preserving information, water treatment etc. The parameters like solubility, pH of the medium, duration of contact, concentration, surface charge and temperature play significant role in domestic, industrial and remedial processes. (There appears to be no documentation that these particles inducing antibody formation directly). They react with the cellular components of immune system like dendritic cells, T-helper cells. The process of activation involves production of cytokines and other mediators which affect the efficacy of immune response subjectively. Investigations reveal their adverse clinical outcomes related to cardiovascular, pulmonary, and oxidative disorders. The other adverse impact of carbon soot and carbon black particles is cytotoxic in nature. At molecular level, ROS production in response to their exposures of these particles damages the cells as well as tissues. These particles are effective to induce genotoxic and epigenetic variations resulting in biomolecular impacts like affecting methylation of DNA and histone proteins as a result influencing immune responses of a biosystem. One needs to work on the mechanism concerning induction of antibody, inflammation and their interaction with different leucocytes like eosinophils, and mast cells, amyloidosis. Faceable global policies are

needed which promote restrictions of the carbon industries to regulate these pollutants because they are necessary evils.

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